

Reduction of Geometric Isomers of Azobenzene at DME

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Manuscript received 29 June 1987, revised 6 April 1988, accepted 3 May 1988

The polarographic reduction behaviour of *cis*- and *trans*-azobenzene(s) revealed different $E_{1/2}$ values. The structural changes have been attributed to cause this variation. *trans*-Azobenzene is known to be more stabilised by resonance compared to *cis*-azobenzene, eventually the former consumes some energy to overcome resonance stabilisation energy and gets reduced at more negative potential.

VARIOUS authors¹⁻³ reported small differences between the $E_{1/2}$ values obtained from the reduction of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of azobenzene. A number of mechanisms have been proposed but not a single explanation is fully convincing to account for the entire set of observations. The present investigation was undertaken to study the difference in the electrode process of the mono-substituted azobenzene isomers besides the unsubstituted ones. The deviations in the reduction behaviour have been highlighted on the basis of structural differences.

Experimental

The current-voltage curves were obtained with a Radelkis OH-105 (Hungary) a.c./d.c. recording polarograph. The a.c. amplitude varied from 5 to 20 ($\pm 2\%$) mV, damping was 1 (a.c. polarography) or 2 (d.c. polarography). The frequency of superimposed a.c. voltage was 60 ± 1 Hz. The scan rate of the recorder was mostly fixed on 200 mV min^{-1} . All measurements pertain to $25^\circ \pm 0.2$ controlled by a thermostatic water-bath. SCE served as the reference electrode. DME had the following capillary characteristics, $1.076 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/3}$ in 0.1 M KCl in an open circuit at $h=70 \text{ cm}$. pH measurements were made with a Elico pH-meter.

Reagents used were either AnalaR or G.R. grade. *trans*-Azobenzene was recrystallised twice from 95% EtOH and chromatographed in petroleum ether through a column of activated alumina (B.D.H., F-20). *cis*-Azobenzene was recrystallised successively from petroleum ether and CCl_4 . *trans*-Monosubstituted-azobenzenes were prepared by the condensation of nitrosobenzene with appropriate substituted-aniline⁴. The compounds were repeatedly recrystallised from aqueous alcohol. *cis*-Monosubstituted-azobenzenes prepared from the *trans*-derivatives by the method of Collins and Jaffe⁵, were stabilised in standard acid solution proposed by Kolthoff and Bruckenstein⁶.

In order to authenticate the sample so prepared the triply recrystallised substances from 95% alcohol

were subjected to purity test by considering sharp melting point and single spot on chromatograms; all compounds analysed for nitrogen were found satisfactory; λ_{max} also compared well with the literature values.

Procedure: The solutions ($1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) of these compounds in $0.1 \text{ M CH}_3\text{COOH}$ - 0.05 M NaClO_4 and 10% $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (some sets in 30% CH_3OH) were prepared. Britton and Robinson buffer was added to maintain a pH range of 1.8-12.0. Triton X-100 (0.005%) was used to suppress maxima in case of substituted isomers. Deaeration was carried out with prepurified nitrogen. Ionic strength $\mu=1$, was adjusted by adding requisite amount of NaClO_4 solution. Polarograms were registered soon after mixing the constituents. The number of electrons transferred during reduction of each substance determined by millicoulometric technique⁷⁻⁹ at a large stirred mercury pool cathode was 2.

Results and Discussion

The limiting currents were found to be diffusion-controlled as seen from (i) $i_{l,sm}$ vs $h^{1/2}$, (ii) small temperature coefficient (1.35-1.55% K^{-1}), (iii) independence of i_d with change in pH and (iv) i_d vs C . The $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{a,s}$ plots resulted in $n=2$ in all the cases, which is in conformity with millicoulometric data.

Further confirmation regarding the reversible reduction was provided by a.c. polarography. According to Matsuda¹⁰,

$$i_s = K F^2 D^{1/2} m^{2/3} t^{2/3} \omega^{1/2} C n^2 E_0 / 2 RT$$

where, $\omega = 2\pi\nu$ ($377 \text{ radians s}^{-1}$, $\nu = 60 \text{ Cs}^{-1}$) and E_0 is the amplitude of superimposed alternating voltage. The calculated values of K (Table 1) are strikingly constant and fall within the established range of the reversible reduction behaviour for both the isomers of azobenzene and its derivatives.

In case of azobenzene(s) under discussion, the diffusion coefficients were found to be 0.417×10^{-5} and $0.578 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for *trans*- and *cis*-isomers,

TABLE 1—PEAK CURRENTS i_p AND K DETERMINED BY A.C. POLAROGRAPHY

Compd.	pH	E_p mV	i_p μ A	K $\times 10^3$
<i>cis</i> -Azobenzene	2.6	20	7.61	5.12
	4.8	20	7.66	5.18
	7.0	10	3.82	5.16
	10.4	5	1.99	5.38
<i>trans</i> -Azobenzene	6.7	20	6.8	5.41
	8.4	10	3.51	5.58
	9.3	5	1.80	5.73
<i>cis</i> -4-Bromoazobenzene	3.2	20	6.95	6.36
	8.4	10	3.09	5.66
<i>trans</i> -4-Bromoazobenzene	3.2	20	6.75	7.24
	8.4	10	2.95	6.33
<i>cis</i> -4-Methylazobenzene	4.5	20	7.72	5.98
	10.2	5	1.75	5.42
<i>trans</i> -4-Methylazobenzene	4.5	20	7.80	5.28
	10.2	5	1.87	5.05

respectively. Similarly, values of 0.229×10^{-5} and 0.315×10^{-5} , 0.417×10^{-5} and 0.440×10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹ were obtained for *trans*- and *cis*-bromo and *trans*- and *cis*-methylazobenzenes, respectively.

The effect of pH on the polarographic wave was studied. Although $E_{1/2}$ values showed a negative shift with increase in pH yet the i_a values remained constant, further supported by the work of Fluorence¹¹.

Several authors¹²⁻¹⁴ evolved the $E_{1/2}$ - pH relationship for azobenzenes. Similar relationships have been found to exist between geometric isomers in the present investigation (Table 2). Two equations for a compound are invariably due to two electronically distinct moieties which could be formed by dissociation of azocompounds.

Electrode mechanism: Azobenzenes may undergo reduction⁷ as per following steps,

with the formation of end-product as hydrazo derivative would result from the addition of (H⁺).

Geometric isomers of monosubstituted-azobenzenes (4-CH₃ and 4-Br) also behave in a similar manner affecting the course of reduction in conformity with the electron-releasing and -attracting tendency of the substituents. It is observed from Table 2 that electron donating substituent increases the difference in $E_{1/2}$ values of the *cis*- and *trans*-forms whereas the difference is decreased by the presence of electron-attracting group.

TABLE 2— $E_{1/2}$ - pH RELATIONSHIP

Compd	$E_{1/2}$ - pH equation	(pH range)
<i>cis</i> -Azobenzene	$E_{1/2} = 0.017 - 0.060 \text{ pH}$	(2-4)
	$- -0.050 - 0.055$	(4-12)
<i>trans</i> -Azobenzene	$- -0.060 - 0.060$	(2-7.5)
	$- -0.09 - 0.052$	(7.5-12)
<i>cis</i> -4-Bromoazobenzene	$- 0.085 - 0.057$	(2-5.2)
	$- -0.010 - 0.040$	(5.2-12)
<i>trans</i> -4-Bromoazobenzene	$- -0.057 - 0.056$	(2-4.6)
	$- -0.10 - 0.050$	(4.6-12)
<i>cis</i> -4-Methylazobenzene	$- -0.036 - 0.061$	(2-6.8)
	$- -0.050 - 0.058$	(6.8-12)
<i>trans</i> -4-Methylazobenzene	$- -0.160 - 0.060$	(2-4.8)
	$- -0.22 - 0.056$	(4.8-12)

Structural differences and reduction of azobenzenes: The salient points to be considered with respect to the structural differences of the two isomers are (i) greater stability of *trans*-azobenzene due to higher resonance stabilisation energy¹⁵, (ii) *trans*-azobenzene is coplanar¹⁶ and *cis*-isomer is rotated out of the nitrogen containing plane by 50° (some authors⁵ report 56°), (iii) larger deviation¹⁷ from the normal angle of N-C-C in the *trans*-isomer and (iv) no bond lengths and angles are exactly equal^{18,19}. Thus the geometry of isomers is dissimilar due to different bond lengths and bond angles, i.e. -N=N- is 1.251 Å (*cis*-) and 1.243 Å (*trans*-) and difference in N-C bond angles is 9° between two isomers. As the normal N=N distance is 1.21 Å, it could be envisaged that *cis*-form is more strained and less stable than *trans*-form. Further, the normal C-N single bond distance is 1.47 Å, while in *cis*- and *trans*-azobenzenes the distances are 1.443 Å and 1.433 Å, respectively, resulting in similar observation as above. Combining this with the factor of coplanarity, resonance stabilisation energy etc. the electron density at N=N linkage is different at both isomers. *cis*-Azobenzene would reduce easily and at less negative potential, while *trans*-isomer requiring some energy to overcome resonance stabilisation would subsequently get reduced in a similar pattern as do the former but at more negative potential.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A. R.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Fellowship.

References

1. A WINKEL and H. SIEBERT, *Chem. Ber* , 1941, 74, 670.
2. F. G. THOMAS and K. G. BOTO in "Chemistry of the Hydrazo, Azo and Azoxy Groups", ed S. PATAI, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1975, p 243.
3. P. J. HILLSON and P. P. BRINBAUM, *Trans Faraday Soc* , 1952, 48, 478
4. H. H. JAFFE and R. W. GARDNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 319.
5. J. H. COLLINS and H. H. JAFFE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc* , 1962, 84, 4708.
6. I. M. KOLTHOFF and S. BRUCKENSTEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc* , 1956, 78, 1.
7. W. U. MALIK and P. N GUPTA, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1974, 54, 417.
8. P. N. GUPTA, C. N. KACHRU and S. A. BHAT, *J. Electrochem. Soc Jpn.*, 1978, 46, 92.
9. P. N. GUPTA and A. RAINA, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 363 ; 1986, 63, 246.
10. H. MATSUDA, *Z. Elektrochem* , 1958, 62, 977.
11. T. M. FLORENCE, *Aust. J. Chem* , 1965, 18, 619.
12. C R. CASTOR and J H. SAYLOR, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1427
13. M. SHIKATA and I. TACHI, *Mem Coll. Agr. Kyoto Imp. Univ.*, 1931, 17, 45.
14. S WAWZONEK and J. D. FREDRICKSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 3985
15. C. C HAMPSON and J. M. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 409.
16. M. ISAKS and H H. JAFFE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 2209.
17. W. J. ORVILLE-THOMAS, "The Structure of Small Molecules", Elsevier, New York, 1966.
18. A. MOSTAD and C. ROMMING, *Acta Chem Scand.*, 1971, 25, 3561.
19. C. J. BROWN, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1966, 21, 146.